

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF EDUCATION OF YOUTH IN THE PATRIOTIC SPIRIT

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Abstract. *In this article, the scholars of the Oriental expressed their valuable thoughts on the education of patriotism in their works. The thoughts of great thinkers on patriotism are the main guidelines for encouraging young people to love the Motherland. This is manifested in pride in the past and present of the homeland, in protecting its interests.*

Keywords: *globalization, patriotism, people’s pedagogy, youth, society, value, universal development, education, heritage, democracy, rule of law, education, personality.*

It is clear to all of us that the XXI century will be the century of globalization and development, when only intellectually highly developed countries will occupy a leading position in the world. Thus, taking the destiny of the New Uzbekistan state into its own hands, it began to build a new life, society, and organize its future as an integral part of the world community. Our hardworking people have the right to live a peaceful, comfortable and peaceful life, taking a place among the developed countries with their selfless work. But this path is a very complicated one, and it requires the priority of self-sacrifice, patriotism, and patriotism from the members of the society. To do this, it is one of the most important tasks of the present day to form the same feelings in young people who will create the future of society. After all, the issue of youth and the issue of raising them in the spirit of patriotism remains important [2, p. 6480-6487]

Today, building a democratic legal state in our country is directly related to educating our youth in the spirit of patriotism. [3, p. 417-421]

For this purpose, activities aimed at strengthening national pride, healthy thinking and worldview in the hearts of our youth, raising them to be strong-willed, selfless and patriotic people who are able to resist various ideological attacks on their conscious living and having an opinion. organization is necessary. Because in our country, educating young people in the spirit of patriotism is the main goal of socio-economic reforms and education. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev said that: “It is known that education of the young generation has always been important and relevant. But in the XXI century in which we live, this issue is really becoming a matter of life and death” [1]. Therefore, the issues of educating young people, educating them in the spirit of patriotism, first of all, are those who actively participate in the construction of this society, who perfectly possess universal values and are loyal to them, who have faith and belief, who have a deep mind, who have pure morals, who have their rights, duties and It is carried out while educating young people who are deeply aware of their responsibilities, and higher educational institutions are considered important social institutions. [4, p. 59]

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan has emphasized that the spiritual foundation of our nation is the ancient and strong support of our state, and has been calling for deep study of the scientific and artistic heritage, ideological and spiritual views of scientists and writers who made an unforgettable contribution to our national history and global development. Because in the activities of our ancestors, high manifestations of patriotism have always been manifested. [5, p. 142-150] Alisher Navai, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, Imam Ismail al-Bukhari, Abu Nasr Farabi,

Abu Ali ibn Sina, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Kaikovus, Muslihiddin Saadi, Abdurrahman Jami, who showed unceasing zeal for the well-being of the country and who encouraged their contemporaries to do the same. It is known that the future of our people, the future development of the country depends on the education and upbringing of our children and their positive development. [6, p. 469-473]

For this, parents, all institutions of the educational system, neighborhoods and the general public should work actively in the family that is engaged in the education of the young generation. [7, p. 197-202]

Human development relies on the rich experiences of Oriental thinkers and folk pedagogy in the field of education. Education creates its rules on the basis of information from the sciences of philosophy, sociology, ethics, aesthetics, physiology, and psychology.

Education is a pedagogical process organized for the purposeful improvement of the individual, which allows regular and systematic influence on the personality of the student [8].

Education is a consistent and goal-oriented process of influence on a person's spiritual and physical development in order to prepare him for production, society and cultural activities. It is inextricably linked with education. It is known that the purpose, content and organization of education are determined by the prevailing social relations [9].

Abdulla Avlani, the Uzbek great pedagogue said: "For us, education is a matter of either life or death, or salvation, or disaster, or happiness - or destruction". It can be seen from this that the issue of education is considered one of the serious issues. [10, p. 2278-3075.]

Education has many meanings, it is a social event, activity, process, value, self-awareness, system, influence, interaction [11, p. 35-42] and so on. Many researchers consider education in a broad social sense. It includes the influence of society as a whole on a person, that is, education is equated with socialization in practice; in a broad pedagogical sense - as an educational work carried out in the system of an educational institution, aimed at a specific goal, in a narrow pedagogical sense - aimed at forming a system of certain qualities, views, beliefs in children; it is understood in an even narrower sense - in the way of solving specific educational tasks. [12]

Independence had an effective impact on the development of all areas of economic and spiritual development of New Uzbekistan. At the same time, he set great responsibilities for literature and writers. The fact that the growing young generation lives as my people, my country, and is brought up in the spirit of confidence in the prosperity of our country depends to a large extent on the educational process [13, p. 203-208]. Of course, in order to fulfill this task, according to the laws and decrees of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the educational system, the educational system, its content and management should be selected and organized in accordance with national traditions, historical and spiritual values. Although today it is considered to be related to the development of self-awareness and independent thinking of young people, to reveal the essence of coordinating the activities of public organizations in the education of students in the spirit of patriotism, it is known that the future of our nation, the future development of the country depends on our children. depends on what kind of education he receives. For this, all educational institutions involved in the education of the young generation, parents and the general public should work actively.

Patriotism means love for the Motherland, pride for its past and present [14, p. 5477-5489].

The sense of patriotism is instilled in young people first of all from the family, from preschool age. Later, this process is formed in general secondary educational institutions and developed in higher educational institutions. In general secondary education institutions, the values that reflect the Motherland as a natural and spiritual environment, that is, the concept that expresses people's love and loyalty to their motherland and their homeland. Patriotism is one of the universal feelings and spiritual values common to all people, peoples, and nations, which has been refined over the centuries. Historically, patriotism is a set of feelings that have been developed in the process of social development related to the fate of their homeland, the struggle of peoples for the inviolability and independence of the territory they live in. This is manifested in pride in the past and present of the homeland, in protecting its interests. [15]

In conclusion, we should say that Eastern thinkers Abul Qasim Firdavsi, Abu Abdullah Rudaki, Nasir Khisrav, Yusuf Khos Khajib, Ahmad Yugnaki, Sakkoki, Alisher Navai, Abdurahman Jami, Makhtumquli, Ogahi and others expressed valuable thoughts on patriotic education in their works. those who did. The thoughts of great thinkers on patriotism are the main guidelines for encouraging young people to love the Motherland.

That is why it is appropriate to use our great and rich heritage, including “The Story of the Prophet Muhammad” and “Hadiths” in the formation of a sense of patriotism in students of higher educational institutions.

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